

SUICIDE PREVENTION RESOURCES AND INFORMATION FOR PROVIDERS

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Warning Signs

From the **National Institute of Mental Health** (For more visit: bit.ly/485hanp)

- Talking about:
 - wanting to die, being a burden to others, great guilt or shame.
- Changing behaviors such as:
 - Making a plan or researching ways to die.
 - Withdrawing from friends, saying goodbye, giving away important items, or making a will.
 - Displaying extreme mood swings.
 - Eating or sleeping more or less.
 - Using drugs or alcohol more often.
 - Taking dangerous risks such as driving extremely fast.
- Feeling:
 - Empty, hopeless, trapped, or having no reason to live.
 - Extremely sad, more anxious, agitated, or full of rage.
 - Unbearable emotional or physical pain.

Lethal Means Counseling & Firearm Safety

- **Counseling on Access to Lethal Means (CALM).** Reducing access to lethal means, such as firearms, can determine whether a person at risk for suicide lives or dies. **Zero Suicide's free training** covers how to talk to people at risk for suicide—and their families—to voluntarily limit access in times of crisis. Visit: bit.ly/4f8Wfml. Or scan the following QR code:
- **Lock to Live** is an online tool that helps people make decisions about temporarily reducing access to potentially dangerous things, like firearms, when they feel hopeless, down, alone, or suicidal. Visit lock2live.org or scan the following QR code:

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Resources for Providers and Primary Care Practices

- **Suicide Prevention Toolkit for Primary Care Practices: A Guide for Primary Care Providers and Medical Practice Managers**, which includes:
 - Suicide prevention implementation checklist and office protocol for suicidal patients (guide and template)
 - Information on suicide epidemiology, effective prevention strategies, risk assessment, and intervention
 - Resources for developing mental health partnerships with other organizations
 - Pocket guide, Safety Plan guide and template, and a crisis support plan
 - Tips/strategies for reimbursement, state-specific resources, and public policy information
 - Information on provider suicide and resources for self-care

Toolkit created by the Western Interstate Commission for Higher Education Mental Health Program (WICHE MHP) & Suicide Prevention Resource Center (SPRC)

National Resources

- For resources on suicide data, ideas for prevention, infographics, and other information visit the **Suicide Prevention Resource Center's** online library: bit.ly/401pQtg
- The **9-8-8 Suicide & Crisis Lifeline** is available 24/7 to offer free and confidential support. Call or text 9-8-8 or go to 988lifeline.org to chat with someone online.
- For finding specific mental health therapists:
 - Visit **Psychology Today** ([psychologytoday.com](https://www.psychologytoday.com)), and find a therapist by race/ethnicity in your state by clicking on "Find a Therapist" and enter your state, then click "all filters". You can filter by race/ethnicity, diagnosis, age, gender, language, and type of therapy.
 - Visit [mentalhealthmatch.com](https://www.mentalhealthmatch.com) and enter your information to be matched with a therapist.
- **The American Foundation for Suicide Prevention** (<https://afsp.org/suicide-prevention-resources/>)
- **American Association of Suicidology**
- **Mental Health America**
- **National Action Alliance for Suicide Prevention**
- **The Dougy Center** – The National Center for Grieving Children and Families
- **The Jason Foundation**
- **The Jed Foundation**
- **Parents, Families, Friends, and Allies United with LGBTQ People (PFLAG)**
- **The Society for the Prevention of Teen Suicide**
- **StopBullying.gov**
- **The Trevor Project**
- **The Tyler Clementi Foundation**
- **Wounded Warrior Project**

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References

(References for "Common Circumstances Before Suicide Involving Firearms Among Black American Adults: Understanding the Challenges as Primary Care Providers")

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